

A Study on Latent Semantic Indexing

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August 2023

1 Literature Review

Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI) is an indexing and retrieval technique that creates a set of terms related to a collection of documents and the terms that go with them in order to examine the relationship between them [5] [22]. In the paper [4], the authors aim to uncover the relationships between a group of documents and the terms that are linked with them by creating Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI). LSI can determine the importance of a document by creating connections between terms used in similar situations [22]. For effective calculation, LSI makes use of the SVD idea, which divides the matrix into its constituent pieces using the mathematical approach known as singular value decomposition (SVD), which enables simpler and more effective calculations [16]. This method is used to extract the latent semantic associations between the terms and documents and lower the dimensionality of the term-document matrix [16].

The concept-based retrieval method of LSI, which relies on a concept rather than a list of words [14], and its dimensionality reduction feature allows for the prioritization of important dimensions and the omission of noisy terms [8]. As mentioned by [15], LSI overcomes the problem of polysemy and synonymy to some extent that occurred with Vector Space Model (VSM). [3] mentions that LSI addresses sparseness, noise and term independence which are some of the problems with information retrieval methods. They have further described that LSI is independent of languages or grammars, and illustrated it by experimenting on a Korean corpus. However, when using dimensionality reduction in Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) in LSI, it is possible to lose the specific information [6]. Furthermore, using the method SVD can lead to a more difficult matrix factorization, which is not practicable for larger datasets. Also, computing SVD itself could limit its scalability [18]. Finding commonality between terms and the ideal dimensionality, such as the value of k , may also be challenging [5]. To deal with complex relationships between the terms and documents could be challenging as well.

In the paper [9], the authors have addressed the problem of concept location in a source code corpus using Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI). In this study, they try to find the code that implements the input concept or query. Given the query as an input, their system will provide the similar documents based on the LSI similarity score. They mention that domain knowledge and concepts were embedded in the source code through identifier names and internal comments, and three preprocessing steps were implemented for source code processing for LSI: 1) extraction of identifiers and comments; 2) identifier separations; and 3) establishing document granularity. They conducted a case study on NCSA Mosaic web browser (version 2.7) and compared the results of LSI with other static code analysis methods of concept location: a search of the program dependency graph and the grep based method. In the paper, they have presented the result of their experiments with user-specified font-based query, generating automated queries and search of the dependence graph. Furthermore, the authors have compared their method with grep-type search and mentions that providing query is as easy as searching with grep and also identifies some concept parts missed by dependence graph search approach [9].

In the paper [15], the authors have addressed the problem of concept location in a source code corpus using Formal Concept Analysis (FCA) and Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI). From the best ranked documents obtained from LSI, they have improved upon [9] by automatically clustering the results and using FCA to present a labeled concept lattice. In their method, LSI creates a search result sequence that corresponds to the notions stated in the programmer's query to the relevant source code

parts. Their method chooses the most important characteristics from those documents and arranges them into a concept lattice produced by FCA in light of the order in which the source code elements are given. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that idea lattices are highly successful (up to four times better than simple ranking) at grouping pertinent data and labeling subjects, concepts, and relationships between them, reducing the irrelevant search results and search effort, providing the user with extra cues when examining search results and easing software maintenance tasks to some extent [15].

Khokale et al. [7] implemented Latent Semantic Analysis in their research, which analyzes, both the user query and the documents aiming to find the pertinent information. Lathi et al. [5] performed a thorough analysis of several information retrieval techniques like Vector Space Model, SMART, Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis and compared them to LSI.

2 Methodology

A corpus is a collection of documents. In this research, the course material corpus of CS-121 is being used which contains lectures, lab works, homeworks, programming assignments, midterm exams, and a final exam. The lectures are available in pdf format, including both text and source codes. All these files are used to make a corpus. For this, texts are extracted and pre-processing is done. After this, term-document matrix is created by assigning value 1 to those only if documents contain word/term. Otherwise assign 0. Let A be the term-document frequency matrix whose rows correspond to terms and whose columns correspond to documents.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

If A be a $m \times n$ matrix, then its Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) is given by three separate matrices; U , Σ (sigma), and V^T [11]. So, by singular value decomposition, any $m \times n$ matrix A can be decomposed as [11];

$$A = U \cdot \Sigma \cdot V^T \quad (2)$$

Where:

- The matrix U is an $m \times m$ orthogonal matrix such that $AA^T = U \wedge U^T$ [22].

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} u_{11} & u_{12} & \dots & u_{1m} \\ u_{21} & u_{22} & \dots & u_{2m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ u_{m1} & u_{m2} & \dots & u_{mm} \end{bmatrix}$$

- The matrix Σ is an $m \times n$ diagonal matrix with singular values on the diagonal. It contains the square root of the eigenvalues of either AA^T or $A^T A$ sorted decreasing order on its diagonal. These are square roots of the eigen values (denoted by lambda sign; which is a scaling factor by which a matrix transforms a vector) of $A^T A$. The non zero values are called singular values [22].

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \sigma_n \end{bmatrix}$$

- The matrix V^T (the transpose of matrix V) is an $n \times n$ orthogonal matrix such that $A^T A = V \wedge V^T$ [22].

$$V^T = \begin{bmatrix} v_{11} & v_{12} & \dots & v_{1n} \\ v_{21} & v_{22} & \dots & v_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ v_{n1} & v_{n2} & \dots & v_{nn} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det(AA^T - \Lambda \cdot I) = 0 \quad (3)$$

We calculate the eigen values using equation 3. After obtaining the eigen values, we obtain the eigen vectors using eigen values. After obtaining eigen values, take the square roots of the eigenvalues. These square roots will become the diagonal entries of the Σ matrix, which captures the importance of the latent semantic dimensions in descending order [17]. V^T is obtained from the eigen vectors. To calculate U orthogonal matrix use the below equation [10],

$$AV = U \cdot \Sigma \quad (4)$$

The three matrices should be truncated to get a lower dimensional representation after all matrices have been generated [12]. Only the largest singular values of the matrices should be included in this truncation [13]. The noise will be reduced and the most important underlying linkages will be captured by this truncation. Let k be a parameter that must be modified according to space. To select k , locate the columns of the U matrix and the rows of the V^T matrix, and then select k , which can be any value lower than the selected value, or itself [22].

The word-topic matrices are then represented using the U matrix that results from dimensionality reduction [19]. The values in the matrix show the degree of association between the word and the subject, with each row of the matrix denoting a term and each column a latent semantic topic [20]. It represents topic by a vector of weighted words [21]. The square root of the sum of the squares of the components is calculated to normalize the matrices, and each row is then divided by that number to guarantee that the length of the row vector is equal to 1 [1]. As a result of the normalization, the associations between the terms and topics is then determined, with each entry reflecting the degree to which a term is associated with a particular latent semantic topic [20].

Let U_k , Σ_K , and V_k^T be the reduced form of the matrix that we obtain after selecting largest k from each of the three matrices. Let \hat{A} be the new approximated term-document matrix that has the result of matrix multiplication of U_k , Σ_K , and V_k^T [22]. Then, document-concept matrix is obtained by performing matrix multiplication of U_K^T and \hat{A} [22]. Lastly, we map a new document query q , which is a query matrix, into the LSI space by transforming query q vector to \hat{q} by using the following equation [22];

$$\hat{q} = U_K^T \cdot q \quad (5)$$

Finally, we calculate the similarity between each document vector that is obtained from document-concept matrix *doc_vector* and new query vector \hat{q} by using the below formula [22]:

$$\text{similarity} = \frac{\text{doc_vector} \cdot \hat{q}}{\|\text{doc_vector}\| \cdot \|\hat{q}\|}$$

3 Results

We used LSI in our corpus both for finding similarity and retrieving information. The purpose of using LSI for similarity was to observe the degree of likeness between lectures tutored in the class by the instructors with the given homeworks, lab works, examinations and assignments. In regards to information retrieval part, we had two main objectives in using LSI: 1) Firstly, we used LSI to retrieve the particular course material where the query is located. In the first case, the query was either question, sentence or code. We also tested if the text associated with particular course material is accurately retrieved by LSI. 2) Secondly, we wanted to determine the lecture material which was closely associated with particular examination, lab works and assignments.

3.1 LSI as a similarity measure

We added LSI in our program with the same data pre-processing and preparation as other similarity measures we previously used (TF-IDF, Doc2Vec, BERT Chunking Method, BERT Truncating Method, BERT Sentence Transformer). Then, we conducted series of experiments as listed in Table 1. In LSI, the vector representation of each word is calculated using co-occurrence matrix. Doc2Vec provides a more powerful embedding vector which can capture word context better than LSI. The BERT models are using bert based embedding.

From Table 2, we can observe that different similarity measures are producing different results on each experiment. Our experiment I comprises of comparison between homework 1 and lecture 1. Lecture 1 is related to introduction to computer, memory and basic problem solving strategies. Homework 1 consists of quizzes with similar concepts presented in Lecture 1. In second experiment, lecture 2 incorporates problem solving, adding comments, print, basic data types of C++; lecture 4 incorporates concepts related to conditionals, data type, logical expressions, relational operators in C++, binary appendix includes numbering system, conversion from one numbering system to another, homework 2 consists of quiz related to basic C++ syntax, programming assignment 1 consists of the requirement to code factorial of a number with permutation concept. As binary appendix contain completely unrelated concept than homework, programming assignment, lectures, the similarity should be low. In experiment III, both Programming Assignment 2 and Lecture 5 is related to concept of loops. In the fifth experiment, lecture 3 and programming assignment 3 is related to math operations, using logical operands, lecture 6 contains concepts and programming related to C++ file I/O. In experiment VI, both programming assignment 4 and lecture 8 is related to functions and array. From this observation, experiment I, III, V, VI should give high similarity score, and experiment II should give comparatively low similarity score. We didn't check concepts in experiment IV and VII as there were many files to include, and generalized their manual inspection and validity from the result of simple experiments.

While inspecting manually, BERT sentence transformer and Doc2Vec is likely giving better performance compared to other measures.

Table 1: List of lecture materials selected for calculating similarity score

Experiment Name.	Description
Experiment I	Between Homework 1 and Lecture 1
Experiment II	Between Homework2, Programming Assignment 1, Lecture 2, Lecture 4, Binary Appendix
Experiment III	Between Programming Assignment 2 and Lecture 5
Experiment IV	Between Midterm 1, Lecture 1, 2, 4, 5, Lab 1, 2, Homework 1, 2 and Programming Assigment 1, 2
Experiment V	Between Programming Assignment 3 and Lecture 3, 6
Experiment VI	Between Programming Assignment 4 and Lecture 8
Experiment VII	Between Midterm 2, Lecture 3, 6, 7, 8, Lab 4, 5, Programming Assignment 3, 4
Experiment VIII	Select All

Table 2: Comparison of different similarity measures and course work success rate

Test/Method	Similarity Measures					
	LSI Method	TF-IDF	Doc2Vec	BERT Chunking Method	BERT Truncating Method	BERT Sentence Transformer
Experiment <i>I</i>	0.0983	0.06	1	0.89	0.67	0.97
Experiment <i>II</i>	0.15	0.22	0.59	0.68	0.65	0.29
Experiment <i>III</i>	0.20	0.13	1	0.89	0.55	0.93
Experiment <i>IV</i>	0.30	0.23	1	0.01	0.59	0.96
Experiment <i>V</i>	0.10	0.07	1	0.03	0.38	0.96
Experiment <i>VI</i>	0.01	0.01	1	0.02	0.33	0.95
Experiment <i>VII</i>	0.17	0.12	1	0.44	0.53	0.97
Experiment <i>VIII</i>	0.05	0.30	0.91	-0.02	0.57	0.96

3.2 LSI for information retrieval

Our second step was to use LSI for information retrieval. For this, we wanted to find a good strategy to select the optimal number of dimensions, k in SVD algorithm. So, we constructed easily observable 5 random short queries and 5 corpus. We wanted to verify the observation from [22] regarding finding the correct value of k , and if it works in random queries and our corpus.

In Table 3, the Query column contains our random queries. Our corpus constitutes of column Input 1 and Input 2.

Table 3: List of random queries and corpus (Input 1 and Input 2) for LSI

Query No.	Query	Input 1	Input 2
Q1	watching sky	Watching movies	watching games
Q2	Write a syntax for for-loop.	This example illustrates how to write syntax for for-loop statement. <code>For i in range(1): print(i)</code>	wirte for-loop
Q3	Main memory persistent.	I am working to know how data is stored in main memory.	Homework 1 file
Q4	Creating a project in visual c++, adding a source code file to the project, adding code to source code file, compiling and running the program.	Programming Assignment 1 file	I am working to know how data is stored in main memory.
Q5	<code>for i in range(10): print(i)</code>	<code>for i in range(5): print(i)</code>	<code>while(i < 5): print(i)</code>

In the Table 3, each query from the *QueryNo.* column is compared with the corpus that contains *Input1* and *Input2* respectively. So, for each query, similarity is calculated between selected query and the corpus. Table 4 represents the result of similarity score obtained when comparison is done between them for different values of k . We see that when the value of k is selected as the length of the corpus, it gives best result. For instance, in case of query *Q5*, it can be observed from Table 4 that as the Input 1 matches mostly with that query (*Q5*), it gives better result when compared to Input 2

Table 4: Result of locating queries in the corpus (given in Table 4) by LSI

Query No.	k=1		k=2	
	Input 1	Input 2	Input 1	Input 2
Q1	1	1	0.86	0.86
Q2	1	1	0.48	0.96
Q3	1	1	0.85	0.54
Q4	1	1	0.99	1.6×10^{-16}
Q5	1	1	0.93	0.66

when value of $k = 2$. This implies that when query is compared with two of the inputs, we are able to get the best similarity score looking at different values of k . In this case, when $k = 2$, it gives the best result for each query. In query ($Q5$), first input is more relevant when compared to second input. So, query ($Q5$) gives more similarity score with first input.

Table 5 lists out the queries that is taken from our course corpus, in which we have experimented using LSI. In *QueryName* column in Table 6, we list out the name of the documents from which queries have been taken. This way, we can use it as a reference to validate when we start calculating the cosine similarity between new document query and files in the corpus. We wanted to test the validity of LSI on text location retrieval task in our corpus. For this, we conducted four small experiments: 1) Query location retrieval on Homework and Final files 2) Query location retrieval on Midterm and Final files 3) Query location retrieval on Lab files 4) Query location retrieval on Lecture files. Similarly, we also identified from which lecture concept the given assignment, exams, lab works and homeworks were being extracted.

3.2.1 Query location retrieval on Homework and Final files

For this experiment, we used three queries from the Table 5, namely Homework 1, Homework2 and Final. The queries are single text/ piece of code fragment. We added the full-text retrieved from Homework 1, Homework 2 and Final pdf files in our LSI corpus. Thus, our corpus incorporated the full text of these 3 files. For testing if the location of piece of corpus can be correctly determined, we experimented with 3 values of k for each of the queries as in Table 6. We found that the queries location from Homework 1, Homework2 and Final were being correctly identified. The paramter k when set to 3 gave the most reasonable similarity score.

Table 5: List of queries and lecture material taken from the CS-121 course

Query Name.	Queries
Homework 1	Data in the main memory is persistent (non-volatile)
Homework 2	What is the datatype for an input file stream object?
Lab 1	Write a program that prints out your course schedule for a single week.
Lab 2	Write a program that prints out all six permutations of the ordering of the following three lines. Output: I saw the big brown bear, the big brown bears saw me, oh! What a frightening experience!
Lab 3	Write a program that prints out business cards for yourself.
Lab 4	Creating a project in visual C++, adding a source code file to the project, adding code to the source code file, compiling and running the program
Lab 5	Write a program that uses a two dimensional array to store the highest and lowest temperatures for each month of the year.
Final	What is the name of the function that every C++ program must have?
Final	Data in the main memory is persistent (non-volatile)
Midterm 1	Rewrite the following code fragment using a while loop and do-while loop instead of a for loop. For (int i = 0; i < 10: i++) {num= num + 2; print (num)}
Midterm 2	List 3 important modes of file creation and define each of them.
Lecture 3	Formatting the output of mathematical expressions using cout filed width and justification.
Lecture 6	Write an interactive c++ program that inputs a name from the user.
Lecture 10	Functions are public, data are private. class Rectangle { private: int width; int length; public: void set(int w, int l); int area(); };

Table 6: Result of text location retrieval on homework and final files

Query Name.	k	Homework 1	Homework 2	Final
Homework 1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.99	0.96	0.47
	3	0.91	0.18	0.32
Homework 2	1	1	1	1
	2	0.97	0.97	0.53
	3	-1×10^{-15}	0.82	0.24
Final	1	1	1	1
	2	0.65	0.90	0.93
	3	0.762	0.40	0.769

3.2.2 Query location retrieval on Midterm and Final files

In the Table 7, final, midterm 1, midterm 2 queries from the *QueryName* column of Table 5 is compared with corpus that contains midterm 1, midterm 2 and final documents. So, for instance, when "Final" is our selected query, it compares with the corpus, and we will get similarity score between that query and each of the documents available in corpus. In this case, when query is compared with corpus, it is seen that Final query matches with the Final document of the corpus. This table further demonstrates that the queries final, homework 1, homework 1, midterm 1 and midterm 2 accurately identifies the documents in the Corpus from which it was extracted. As with previous observation, if we set the value of k to the length of the corpus, we are getting most rational similarity score.

Table 7: Result of text location retrieval on final and midterm files

Query Name.	k	Midterm 1	Midterm 2	Final
Final and Homework 1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.36	0.71	0.87
	3	0.36	0.22	0.76
Final	1	1	1	1
	2	0.19	0.58	0.78
	3	0.16	0.60	0.74
Midterm 1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.92	0.68	0.46
	3	0.91	0.60	0.45
Midterm 2	1	1	1	1
	2	0.31	0.67	0.85
	3	0.17	0.76	0.62

3.2.3 Query location retrieval on Lab files

In the Table 8, lab queries from the *QueryName* column of Table 5 is compared with corpus that contains all lab documents. So, for instance, when "lab1" is our selected query, it compares with the corpus, and we will get similarity score between that query and each of the documents available in corpus. In this case, when query is compared with corpus, it is seen that Lab 1 query matches best with the Lab1 document of the corpus when $k = 7$. This table further demonstrates that the queries lab 1, lab 2, lab 3 and lab 5 accurately identifies the documents in the Corpus from which it was extracted. Lab 4 query is being identified as belonging to Lab 6.

Table 8: Result of text location retrieval on the lab files

Query Name.	k	Lab 1	Lab 2	Lab 3	Lab 4	Lab 5	Lab 6	Lab 7
Lab 1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.98	0.96	0.99	0.91	0.87	0.55	0.98
	3	0.98	0.97	0.99	0.22	0.90	0.48	0.99
	4	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.104	0.44	0.25	0.95
	5	0.96	0.943	0.641	0.101	0.412	0.24	0.76
	6	0.96	0.902	0.643	0.101	0.411	0.24	0.244
	7	0.92	0.602	0.59	0.096	0.3906	0.228	0.1815
Lab 2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.94	0.91	0.49	0.97
	3	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.3	0.90	0.44	0.97
	4	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.09	0.25	0.14	0.85
	5	0.93	0.96	0.22	0.05	0.15	0.09	0.94
	6	0.89	0.96	0.198	0.056	0.15	0.088	-0.06
	7	0.13	0.94	0.17	0.04	0.11	0.06	0.05
Lab 3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.99	0.96	0.99	0.91	0.878	0.55	0.98
	3	0.99	0.97	0.99	0.22	0.904	0.48	0.99
	4	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.08	0.350	0.206	0.904
	5	0.59	0.52	0.98	0.08	0.32	0.18	0.09
	6	0.59	0.47	0.98	0.07	0.32	0.18	0.12
	7	0.37	0.49	0.97	0.07	0.31	0.18	0.148
Lab 4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.82	0.75	0.87	0.64	0.57	0.86	0.95
	3	0.85	0.805	0.89	0.13	0.67	0.78	0.95
	4	0.55	0.53	0.53	0.1229	0.62	0.74	0.899
	5	0.52	0.49	0.43	0.1223	0.62	0.74	0.53
	6	0.501	0.37	0.42	0.116	0.58	0.70	0.43
	7	0.36	0.36	0.43	0.11	0.58	0.70	0.43
Lab 5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.938	0.905	0.50	0.97
	3	0.99	0.97	0.98	0.186	0.93	0.42	0.98
	4	0.81	0.81	0.78	0.14	0.72	0.33	0.98
	5	0.72	0.68	0.69	0.14	0.72	0.33	0.53
	6	0.71	0.71	0.63	0.69	0.14	0.71	0.23
	7	0.44	0.64	0.68	0.13	0.69	0.32	0.26

3.2.4 Query location retrieval on Lecture files

In the Table 9, lecture queries from the *QueryName* column is compared with corpus that contains all lecture documents. So, for instance, when "Lec 3" is our selected query, it compares with the corpus, and we will get similarity score between that query and each of the documents available in corpus. In this case, when query is compared with corpus, it is seen that lecture 3 query matches best with the lecture 3 document of the corpus when $k = 10$. This table further demonstrates that the queries lecture 3, lecture 6 and lecture 10 accurately identifies the documents in the Corpus from which it was extracted.

Table 9: Result of text location retrieval on the lecture files

Query	k	Lec.1	Lec.2	Lec.3	Lec.4	Lec.5	Lec.6	Lec.7	Lec.8	Lec.9	Lec.10
Lec. 3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.9	0.48	0.978	0.842	0.93	0.95	0.90	0.99	0.86	0.088
	3	0.9	0.63	0.98	0.85	0.97	0.98	0.92	0.26	0.80	0.041
	4	0.43	0.70	0.917	0.80	0.94	0.96	0.90	0.24	0.78	0.03
	5	0.43	0.46	0.91	0.65	-0.06	0.902	0.46	0.24	0.46	0.03
	6	0.43	0.39	0.89	0.608	-0.012	0.75	0.11	0.24	-0.02	0.03
	7	0.43	0.33	0.88	-0.004	-0.003	0.69	0.115	0.24	-0.03	0.03
	8	0.43	0.28	0.88	-0.004	-0.000	0.69	-0.004	0.24	-0.004	0.03
	9	0.42	0.189	0.869	-1×10^{-4}	-1.5×10^{-4}	-8×10^{-4}	-4×10^{-4}	0.23	0.03	-4.9×10^{-5}
	10	0.42	3.38×10^{-16}	0.86	-1.86×10^{-16}	1.14×10^{-16}	-2.25×10^{-16}	-3.2×10^{-16}	0.23	-5×10^{-16}	0.03
Lec. 6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.99	0.69	0.99	0.95	0.95	0.99	0.99	0.984	0.96	0.33
	3	0.88	0.74	0.99	0.81	0.95	0.96	0.87	0.022	0.73	0.12
	4	0.47	0.75	0.91	0.75	0.94	0.93	0.85	0.015	0.75	0.11
	5	0.33	0.85	0.67	0.80	0.71	0.82	0.917	0.008	0.87	0.083
	6	0.28	0.85	0.6	0.77	0.52	0.84	0.84	0.004	0.68	0.07
	7	0.24	0.83	0.49	0.69	0.40	0.80	0.803	0.6	0.00	0.54
	8	0.22	0.86	0.46	0.64	0.36	0.77	0.60	0.0006	0.4	0.05
	9	0.13	0.77	0.26	0.36	0.21	0.89	0.337	-3×10^{-5}	0.23	0.03
	10	0.12	0.42	0.25	0.34	0.20	0.84	0.31	-1.2×10^{-16}	0.22	0.03
Lec. 10	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	0.47	0.93	0.35	0.65	0.49	0.44	0.55	0.16	0.62	0.99
	3	0.45	0.84	0.28	0.62	0.42	0.38	0.51	0.09	0.62	0.98
	4	0.09	0.83	0.28	0.62	0.36	0.38	0.51	0.09	0.49	0.98
	5	0.09	0.64	0.28	0.55	0.013	0.37	0.31	0.09	0.34	0.98
	6	0.096	0.63	0.28	0.55	-8×10^{-5}	0.3	0.23	0.09	0.18	0.98
	7	0.094	0.56	0.28	0.001	0.007	0.33	0.23	0.09	0.18	0.97
	8	0.09	0.58	0.2	0.0003	-0.003	0.33	0.28	0.09	0.137	0.95
	9	0.09	0.56	0.277	-0.00	-0.0004	0.12	0.28	0.09	0.13	0.95
	10	0.09	5×10^{-16}	0.2	-3×10^{-17}	-3×10^{-17}	0.12	0.28	0.09	0.13	0.95

In the next phase of our experiments, we wanted to identify the lecture which closely resembled the lecture assignments including midterms, lab works, homeworks, assignments and final.

3.2.5 Identification of lecture assignments closely related to Lecture 1 to 5

In the Table 10, each document from the *QueryFile* column is compared with corpus that contains Lecture 1, Lecture 2, Lecture 3, Lecture 4 and Lecture 5 documents. In this table, we can see that the document Midterm 1 is closely related to Lecture 2, Lab 1 is closely related to Lecture 3 and Homework 1 belongs to Lecture 1.

Table 10: Similarity score of assignment document with corpus Lecture 1-5

QueryFile	Lec.1	Lec.2	Lec.3	Lec.4	Lec.5
Midterm 1	0.22	0.82	0.51	0.40	0.13
Lab 1	0.27	0.39	0.79	0.48	0.38
Homework 1	0.79	0.29	0.52	0.39	0.17

3.2.6 Identification of lecture assignments closely related to Lecture 6 to 10

In the Table 11, each document from the *QueryFile* column is compared with corpus that contains Lecture 6, Lecture 7, Lecture 9, Lecture 9 and Lecture 10 documents. In this table, we can see that final exam has more similarity with lecture 10, lab 7 work has more similarity with Lecture 6, assignment 4 has more similarity with lecture 6 and midterm 2 is closely related to lecture 10.

Table 11: Similarity score of assignment document with corpus Lecture 6-10

QueryFile	Lec.6	Lec.7	Lec.8	Lec.9	Lec.10
Final	0.18	0.15	0.16	0.127	0.97
Lab 7	0.83	0.24	-3×10^{-17}	0.62	0.15
Assignment 4	0.85	0.31	0.16	0.45	0.41
Midterm 2	0.18	0.35	0.34	0.27	0.91

4 Threats to validity

We have implemented LSI and inspected the result manually on a limited corpus. The results of both the similarity and lecture location tasks were inspected manually. As the ground truth was subjective, this could cause variation in the determination of the performance of the algorithm. Due to the limited corpus, the probability of facing a query with non of the words present in the corpus is high. Currently, this situation is handled by returning the similarity score of 0. The other limitation to this approach is as query term matrix is a co-occurrence matrix constructed by counting words present in each document, the query term matrix is not semantical. Any new word with similar meaning is not placed in query term matrix. We have also found that the selection parameter ‘k’ for the number of singular values or optimal number of dimension plays high role in the calculation of the similarity score. The good rule of thumb validated by our experiments is to use $\min(\text{number of rows of } U, \text{ number of cols of } V^T)$ if our matrix A is broken down into $U \cdot \Sigma \cdot V^T$ [22]. This implies that if we have large number of corpus, the value of ‘k’ should be large as well for obtaining a reasonable similarity score. This can cause memory issues in large corpus set. Also, choosing any value of ‘k’ beyond the rank of the matrix is not possible [2].

5 Conclusion

While Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI) is better for information retrieval, for our corpus, Doc2Vec and transformer-based models like sentence transformer gave best result while comparing the documents to find the similarities between them. We compared Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI) with other similarity measure techniques such as BERT, Doc2Vec, TF-IDF and so on. From that, we can conclude that Doc2Vec and transformer models are likely able to give better result than LSI for similarity task. LSI is also used for information retrieval. For this, we performed several experiments on corpus to select the optimal number of dimensions for our study. Based on the results obtained, we found that LSI technique works well in retrieving the information based on the queries and identifying the documents in the corpus. During these experiments, we were also able to obtain the correct value of k that suits for our corpus. When k (dimension) equals the length of our corpus, it gives a better result that

helps to find out the document from which it has been extracted. Lastly, we also retrieved the lecture document which were most similar to the given course assignment.

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